

Quantifying the Impact of Interdisciplinary Research

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ABSTRACT

Globally, there is an increasing interest in integrating the gender dimension in research content (GDRC). As a first step towards monitoring progress in this area, a new indicator measuring the proportion of a country's scientific publications integrating a gender dimension in their subject matter was developed for the European Commission's *She Figures 2015* publication. This indicator is based on a keyword-based query covering both sex-related terms (biological characteristics of both women and men) and gender-related terms (social/cultural factors of both women and men). The final GDRC dataset consisted of some 212,600 distinct publications including a gender dimension in their research content. Findings suggest that integrating a gender dimension into research content is relatively rare. Unsurprisingly, it was less common for scientific articles in the fields of agricultural sciences, engineering and technology, and natural sciences to do so, and more common in the social sciences.

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INTRODUCTION

Within the context of the European Commission's Eighth Framework Programme for Research and Technological Development (Horizon 2020), activities towards achieving gender equality are being implemented along three main axes: fostering gender balance in research teams; ensuring gender balance in decision-making; and integrating gender analysis in research and innovation (R&I) content (European Commission & Directorate-General for

¹ The production of this methodology for the *She Figures 2015* was led by Science-Metrix, with extensive contributions from the Directorate-General for Research and Innovation of the European Commission; EIGE; Eurostat; the Helsinki Group on Gender in Research and Innovation and their Statistical Correspondents; ICF International, KU Leuven and the OECD.

Research and Innovation, 2014). Where relevant, Horizon 2020 participants must now specify in their grant proposals how the gender dimension (i.e. taking into account as relevant the biological characteristics and the social and cultural features of both women and men) will be

integrated into the subject matter of their projects (European Parliament and the Council of the European Union, 2013). As such, it is highly relevant to begin monitoring trends in the extent to which researchers incorporate such aspects into their research content. This will provide evidence to allow the monitoring of the extent to which the gender dimension appears in the research content of the scientific outputs produced by countries.

In the context of the production of the *She Figures 2015* publication (European Commission, 2016), a new indicator was developed to monitor the extent to which researchers integrate a gender dimension into their research content. Some experts involved in the consultation process (acknowledged at the beginning of this paper) expressed concerns about the scope of the topics that should be included in the gender dimension, which led to a consideration of the definitions of ‘sex’, ‘gender’, ‘sex/gender analysis’, and ‘gender dimension in research’ in the glossary of the document *Gender Equality in Horizon 2020* (European Commission & Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, 2014).

METHODS

The following sections provide an overview of some of the key methodological considerations in the development of this indicator; however, for a more complete summary, the reader is referred to the comprehensive methodological document produced for the *She Figures 2015* study (Campbell, 2015).

Bibliographic data on peer-reviewed scientific publications is necessary for producing data on this topic. Thomson Reuters’ Web of Science (WoS) was selected for this study because it provides cited references for each document it includes (e.g. articles or chapters published in a journal or book series), as well the institutional affiliations of authors. The two-step process to construct the query for the retrieval of scientific publications in which a gender dimension is addressed comprises

1. the identification of an initial set (i.e. ‘seed’) of highly relevant papers, and
2. the extraction of gender-specific terms through an analysis of the textual content present in the seed, which are then used to expand the seed to obtain the final dataset.

Based on the definitions provided in the Horizon 2020 documentation cited above, the gender dimension in research content includes both the concepts of sex and gender as well as the concept of sex/gender analysis in humans.

In addition to research outputs focused on a well-defined gender topic (e.g. feminism, gender pay gap, gender equality), research content in which a distinction or a comparison is made between men and women either in the title, abstract, or author keywords of scientific publications were deemed relevant. Following extensive consultation with the *She Figures 2015* expert committee, research outputs studying the animal kingdom (e.g. feminisation of fish populations) as well as other non-human biological entities (e.g. plants), were excluded in the construction of the dataset on the gender dimension in research content. Moreover, scientific papers investigating medical conditions specific to one gender (e.g. menopause, erectile dysfunction) were also not to be considered pertinent to the dataset as the inclusion of those

would result in the inclusion of a very large portion of scientific publications in the medical fields.

Creation of the seed dataset

All publications indexed in the WoS were classified into six large domains (Applied Sciences, Arts & Humanities, Economic & Social Sciences, General, Health Sciences and Natural Sciences), then further divided into 22 fields and 176 subfields using Science-Metrix's journal-based classification (Archambault, Beauchesne, & Caruso, 2011). This classification is mutually exclusive – that is, each article is classified into one and only one set of domain, field and subfield. Using the fields of science and technology (FOS) classification in the *Frascati Manual* (OECD, 2002), as well as the revised classification (OECD, 2007), the subfields in Science-Metrix's classification were then matched to their corresponding FOS as defined in the *Frascati Manual's* 2007 description. Thus, this indicator was computed for each of the following six FOS:

- (NS) Natural sciences;
- (ET) Engineering and Technology;
- (MS) Medical sciences;
- (AS) Agricultural sciences; • (SS) Social sciences; and
- (H) Humanities.

The first step in identifying scientific publications relevant to the gender dimension in research content was to identify fields and subfields directly related to gender research. The subfield of Gender Studies under the field of Social Sciences was found to be directly relevant, and contained 6,023 publications discussing a gender-related topic (for the period 2002–2013). A validation check (title and abstract reading) of a randomly selected sample of 100 articles was performed to enable the confirmation of the pertinence of the publications in this subfield.

In the subsequent step, a search for journal names containing the term 'gender' was executed in the WoS. The scope of each journal was evaluated either by accessing its website or, when this was not possible, by examining the journal's publications (Table 1). Based on the scope of the journals, a verdict determining if the papers published in each journal were pertinent to the gender dimension in research content was assigned. All the publications contained in the relevant journals (2,150 for 2002–2013) were then added to the seed dataset.

Table 1. WoS journals containing the term *gender* in their name

Journal name	Papers (2002–2013)	Verdict
FOCUS ON GENDER: PARENT AND CHILD CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE SOCIALIZATION OF EMOTIONAL COMPETENCE	7	ok
PEDIATRIC GENDER ASSIGNMENT: A CRITICAL REAPPRAISAL	19	ok
GENDER AND LANGUAGE	54	ok
POLITICS & GENDER	92	ok
JOURNAL OF WOMENS HEALTH & GENDER-BASED MEDICINE	121	ok
INDIAN JOURNAL OF GENDER STUDIES	147	ok
JOURNAL OF GENDER STUDIES	234	ok
GENDER MEDICINE	266	ok
GENDER PLACE AND CULTURE	333	NO (also on race, ethnicity, sexuality, etc)
GENDER WORK AND ORGANIZATION	346	ok
GENDER & SOCIETY	394	ok
GENDER AND EDUCATION	468	ok

Source: Compiled by Science-Metrix from WoS data (Thomson Reuters)

Next, journals that published articles classified in the subfield of Gender Studies, and which were different from those identified previously, were retrieved. The scope of these journals was assessed in the same manner as previously described in order to evaluate the relevance of their content. The 3,700 articles published in appropriate journals between 2002 and 2013 were subsequently added to the seed dataset (Table 2).

Table 2. WoS journals containing publications classified under the subfield Gender Studies

Journal name	Papers (2002–2013)	Verdict
FEMINISTISCHE STUDIEN	101	ok
FEMINIST THEORY	101	ok
NOUVELLES QUESTIONS FEMINISTES	141	ok
INTERNATIONAL FEMINIST JOURNAL OF POLITICS	163	ok
ASIAN JOURNAL OF WOMENS STUDIES	163	ok
HYPATIA-A JOURNAL OF FEMINIST PHILOSOPHY	177	ok
FRONTIERS-A JOURNAL OF WOMEN STUDIES	179	ok
FEMINIST STUDIES	213	ok
MEN AND MASCULINITIES	215	ok
FEMINIST REVIEW	230	ok
SEXUALITIES	232	ok
AUSTRALIAN FEMINIST STUDIES	237	ok
EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF WOMENS STUDIES	256	ok
FEMINISM & PSYCHOLOGY	408	ok
SIGNS	504	ok
JOURNAL OF SEX RESEARCH	510	ok
WOMENS STUDIES INTERNATIONAL FORUM	604	ok

Source: Compiled by Science-Metrix from WoS data (Thomson Reuters)

The last phase in building the seed dataset involved using Medline's controlled vocabulary medical subject heading (MeSH) terms to identify gender-related scientific articles indexed in the WoS and in Medline. A search for MeSH terms containing every variant of gender, femin*, women and men allowed for the identification of 18 relevant MeSH terms (Table 3). To enable the extraction of publications using MeSH terms in the WoS, all publications in Medline were

matched to their corresponding entry in the WoS. The pertinence of the papers retrieved by each MeSH term was evaluated through a title and abstract analysis on a random sample of papers. The only MeSH terms that were not satisfactory were Feminization and Pregnant Women.

Table 3. MeSH terms, the number of papers associated with them in the WoS and the verdict for addition of the associated publications in the seed dataset

Mesh descriptor term	Papers (2002-2013)	Verdict
Feminine Hygiene Products	9	NO
Sexual and Gender Disorders	17	ok
Dentists, Women	29	ok
Femininity	51	ok
Feminization	68	NO, medical explanation of feminization (most of the time not in human)
Transgendered Persons	113	ok
Feminism	207	ok
Physicians, Women	323	ok
Men's health	390	ok
Women's Rights	403	ok
Women's Health Services	573	ok
Women, Working	627	ok
Pregnant Women	694	NO, as decided by expert committee
Battered Women	991	ok
Women	1,680	ok
Gender Identity	2,045	ok
Women's Health	4,480	ok

Source: Compiled by Science-Metrix from WoS data (Thomson Reuters)

Following the addition of the articles captured by the selected MeSH terms, the seed dataset consisted of 17,900 distinct publications. A publication may have been retrieved multiple times by the different techniques (subfield, journals or MeSH terms) but was only counted once.

Creation of the final dataset

In this phase, the seed dataset was expanded using a query searching for gender-related terminology in the title, abstract and author keywords of the publications indexed in the WoS. Highly relevant terms were identified using the term frequency–inverse document frequency (TF-IDF) statistic. The TF-IDF statistic determines the importance of a given expression (a term or set of terms) in a specific set of documents (i.e. the seed dataset) relative to a reference collection of documents (the WoS). The relevance of an expression increases proportionally to the number of times it appears in the seed dataset but is offset by the frequency of the word in the reference collection. This operation increases the detection of rare and specific expressions. Two lists of expressions were tested using the TF-IDF weight. The first list consists of the EIGE draft thesaurus on gender equality terms (which contains more than 600 terms). The second list consists of a set of about 10 million noun phrases (i.e. scientific expressions) extracted from the titles, abstracts and author keywords of publications in the WoS.

The keywords of the highest relevance (i.e. those with the highest TF-IDF weight, some of which are shown in Table 4) are the most promising expressions to identify gender-related publications. As one goes down the list, there is a threshold (not necessarily well defined) at which point the expressions are not specific enough to be used in the search query aimed at expanding the seed dataset (highlighted in red).

Table 4. Items with low TF-IDF weight not included in the keyword query

EIGE keywords		WoS extracted noun phrases	
Keyword	Weight	Keyword	Weight
Transsexual	12.59	Intimate partner	14.89
•	•	•	•
•	•	•	•
Demographic change	7.62	Risk taking	10.22
Witness	7.62	Awakening response	10.22
Spending	7.60	Problematise	10.22
Career planning	7.59	Source care	10.22
Migrant worker	7.54	Meaning practice	10.22
Families	7.52	Low libido	10.22
Risk group	7.52	Qualitative method	10.22
•	•	•	•
•	•	•	•

Source: Compiled by Science-Metrix from WoS data (Thomson Reuters)

Each of the promising expressions was tested manually by retrieving publications in which the expression appeared in their titles, abstracts or author keywords (using wildcards to ensure all wording with the same root would be retrieved). For each search term, a seasoned analyst read the title and abstract of a random sample of the retrieved publications to judge their pertinence. When the majority of the retrieved publications were judged relevant, the search expression was included in the keyword-based query. The experts group expressed concerns that the approach using the TF-IDF weight could induce a bias towards the seed dataset (Gender Studies subfield + specialist journals + MeSH terms), so the selection of relevant search expressions was re-iterated using the TF-IDF weight, resulting in around 220 search expressions being included in the query. The final step in the query consisted of deleting articles about the animal kingdom that were not filtered by the field/subfield exclusion criteria.

Recall and precision

The dataset's quality was assessed via two parameters often used in information retrieval. The recall (i.e. the percentage of false negatives, or relevant papers that were not retrieved) of the seed dataset was measured by taking the intersection of the publications in the seed dataset with those retrieved by the keyword-based query over the size of the seed dataset (i.e. the percentage of the seed retrieved with the keyword-based query). This facilitates the assessment of how well selected search expressions capture the core literature related to Gender Studies and gender-related MeSH terms. The recall was also assessed at the journal level by measuring the

percentage of articles captured by the keyword query that are present in the journals that were included in the seed dataset.

The recall of the seed dataset is near 60% (Table 5), which is around what is expected for a dataset in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH). Indeed, it is difficult to achieve higher recall for subjects related to the SSH, as the expressions used in this domain are usually less specific to a particular area of research than the expressions used in the Natural Sciences and Engineering or Health Sciences domains. Adding more keywords (likely more generic terms) to increase the recall would be detrimental to the dataset, as this would lead to the concomitant retrieval of false positives and a subsequent reduction in precision. The recall of the specialist journals is also satisfactory, with the majority of them having a recall above the 60% mark.

Table 5. Recall of the seed dataset (i.e. gender studies subfield, specialist journals and MeSH terms) and of each of the specialist journals using the keyword-based query

Dataset/Journal	Articles from KW query	Total articles	Recall
Seed dataset	10,453	17,885	58.4%
GENDER & SOCIETY	375	394	95.2%
MEN AND MASCULINITIES	202	215	94.0%
GENDER AND LANGUAGE	50	54	92.6%
JOURNAL OF GENDER STUDIES	215	234	91.9%
EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF WOMENS STUDIES	235	256	91.8%
GENDER WORK AND ORGANIZATION	313	346	90.5%
SEXUALITIES	208	232	89.7%
GENDER AND EDUCATION	405	468	86.5%
NOUVELLES QUESTIONS FEMINISTES	116	141	82.3%
ASIAN JOURNAL OF WOMENS STUDIES	132	163	81.0%
WOMENS STUDIES INTERNATIONAL FORUM	484	604	80.1%
FEMINIST REVIEW	180	230	78.3%
FEMINIST THEORY	79	101	78.2%
FEMINISTISCHE STUDIEN	79	101	78.2%
INTERNATIONAL FEMINIST JOURNAL OF POLITICS	127	163	77.9%
POLITICS & GENDER	66	92	71.7%
FOCUS ON GENDER: PARENT AND CHILD CONTRIBUTIONS TO	5	7	71.4%
INDIAN JOURNAL OF GENDER STUDIES	102	147	69.4%
FEMINISM & PSYCHOLOGY	266	408	65.2%
GENDER MEDICINE	171	266	64.3%
HYPATIA-A JOURNAL OF FEMINIST PHILOSOPHY	110	177	62.1%
JOURNAL OF SEX RESEARCH	315	510	61.8%
SIGNS	241	504	47.8%
FEMINIST STUDIES	97	213	45.5%
AUSTRALIAN FEMINIST STUDIES	106	237	44.7%
FRONTIERS-A JOURNAL OF WOMEN STUDIES	52	179	29.1%
JOURNAL OF WOMENS HEALTH & GENDER-BASED MEDICINE	34	121	28.1%
PEDIATRIC GENDER ASSIGNMENT: A CRITICAL REAPPRAISAL	5	19	26.3%

Source: Compiled by Science-Metrix from WoS data (Thomson Reuters)

The precision (i.e. one minus the percentage of false positives, or irrelevant papers that were accidentally retrieved) of the dataset was examining the titles and abstracts of a random sample of 100 articles (Table 6). If the subject(s) of a paper did not relate to the above definition of GDRC, it was considered as a false positive. The precision was measured for the dataset as a

whole as well as for the fields in which GDRC papers are less likely to be found, such as in Information & Communication Technologies, Agriculture, Fisheries & Forestry, Engineering, and Earth & Environmental Science. The dataset as a whole has an excellent precision of 97%. The precision decreases a little for unusual fields, but since they are almost all above 70% and they do not represent a large proportion of the final dataset, this should not be a cause for concern.

Table 6. Precision of the GDRC dataset as a whole and for some fields in which relevant papers are less likely

Field	Precision	Sample size
Whole dataset	97%	100
Agriculture, Fisheries & Forestry	70%	50
Information & Communication Technologies	78%	50
Earth & Environmental Sciences	74%	50
Engineering	84%	50
Mathematics & Statistics	60%	50
Physics & Astronomy	80%	50

Source: Compiled by Science-Metrix from WoS data (Thomson Reuters)

All proportions are underestimated to a similar extent across countries for literature written in English. Care was taken not to bias the recall (i.e. the fraction of GDRC-relevant literature that was effectively retrieved and measured) in favour of specific countries.

Formula

Once the dataset is defined, the computation of the proportion of a country's publications integrating a gender dimension in its research content for a given year and field of science (FOS) is straightforward:

Table 7. Distribution of publications in the GDRC dataset across fields of science

Field	Papers	Share of field	Share of dataset
Total	212,673	N/A	100.0%
Clinical Medicine	91,162	2.9%	42.9%
Public Health & Health Services	33,546	10.5%	15.8%
Social Sciences	28,674	8.8%	13.5%
Psychology & Cognitive Sciences	20,961	7.9%	9.9%
Biomedical Research	10,685	0.9%	5.0%
Economics & Business	6,371	2.6%	3.0%
Communication & Textual Studies	5,363	5.2%	2.5%
Historical Studies	4,811	5.1%	2.3%
Philosophy & Theology	1,630	2.6%	0.8%
General Science & Technology	1,169	0.6%	0.5%
Information & Communication Technologies	1,108	0.2%	0.5%
General Arts, Humanities & Social Sciences	922	6.5%	0.4%
Enabling & Strategic Technologies	874	0.1%	0.4%
Visual & Performing Arts	715	3.4%	0.3%
Earth & Environmental Sciences	615	0.1%	0.3%
Engineering	537	0.1%	0.3%
Built Environment & Design	411	0.6%	0.2%
Biology	402	0.1%	0.2%
Chemistry	382	0.0%	0.2%
Mathematics & Statistics	267	0.1%	0.1%
Physics & Astronomy	234	0.0%	0.1%
Agriculture, Fisheries & Forestry	129	0.0%	0.1%
UNKNOWN	1,705	2.1%	0.8%

Source: Compiled by Science-Metrix from WoS data (Thomson Reuters)

As shown in Table 7, the fields that are present in high proportion relative to their size (column *Share of field*) are primarily from the Social Sciences and Humanities domain. Other than Clinical Medicine, the most represented fields (column *Share of dataset*) are Public Health & Health Services, Social Sciences, Psychology & Cognitive Sciences, and Biomedical Research, which is where one would expect most of the gender-related publications to be published. It is also interesting to note that the keyword query did catch a small number of articles from fields in which the presence of gender-related topics is less likely, such as Information & Communication Technologies, Earth & Environmental Sciences or Chemistry.

Table 8 shows the proportion of scientific publications that include a gender dimension in their content, by country and by field of science & technology over two time periods (2002–2005 and 2010–2013).

Table 8. Proportion of a country's scientific publications including a gender dimension in their research content, by field of science, 2002-2005 and 2010-2013

	Natural sciences		Engineering and technology		Medical sciences		Agricultural sciences		Social sciences		Humanities	
	02–05	10–13	02–05	10–13	02–05	10–13	02–05	10–13	02–05	10–13	02–05	10–13
World	0.1	0.2	0.0	0.1	2.8	3.9	0.0	0.0	6.8	7.2	3.9	3.9
EU-28	0.1	0.2	0.0	0.1	2.5	3.8	0.0	0.0	5.6	6.2	2.7	3.2
BE	0.2	0.2	0.0	0.1	2.4	3.5	0.0	0.0	4.3	5.1	1.6	2.4
BG	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.2	1.7	2.5	0.0	0.0	8.8	1.6	6.3	6.3
CZ	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	1.6	3.1	0.1	0.0	5.5	5.5	2.9	2.5
DK	0.3	0.3	0.1	0.1	4.5	5.3	0.0	0.0	2.6	4.6	2.5	3.6
DE	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	1.9	3.0	0.0	0.0	4.6	5.1	2.0	1.4
EE	0.3	0.1	0.0	0.3	3.8	7.3	0.0	0.0	8.1	6.8	0.0	1.7
IE	0.1	0.2	0.0	0.0	2.9	4.8	0.0	0.0	8.5	7.0	2.5	5.0
EL	0.1	0.3	0.0	0.1	2.6	4.3	0.0	0.0	3.8	4.9	4.4	3.0
ES	0.1	0.2	0.0	0.1	2.6	4.1	0.0	0.0	4.2	6.5	0.7	2.4
FR	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	1.9	2.8	0.0	0.0	3.2	4.1	1.6	1.9
HR	0.1	0.3	0.0	0.1	3.5	4.3	0.0	0.0	8.7	8.5	0.0	3.5
IT	0.1	0.2	0.0	0.1	2.3	3.1	0.0	0.0	3.5	4.4	1.4	1.6
CY	0.2	0.2	0.0	0.0	7.2	7.2	0.0	0.0	6.0	6.7	0.0	1.0
LV	0.1	0.3	0.0	0.0	1.2	2.5	0.0	0.0	16.7	3.5	0.0	7.7
LT	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.4	4.5	5.5	0.0	0.0	6.7	3.6	10.5	0.0
LU	0.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.2	5.2	0.0	0.0	3.6	5.4	0.0	2.9
HU	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	2.1	4.1	0.0	0.0	5.6	4.2	3.4	2.2
MT	2.2	1.3	0.0	0.0	4.4	7.1	0.0	0.0	6.7	3.7	0.0	0.0
NL	0.2	0.4	0.1	0.1	3.2	4.3	0.0	0.0	5.4	5.5	2.8	2.6
AT	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.2	2.1	3.4	0.0	0.0	4.4	6.6	4.2	1.8
PL	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	2.0	3.7	0.0	0.0	4.7	4.9	3.9	2.5
PT	0.1	0.2	0.0	0.1	2.3	5.6	0.0	0.0	3.8	4.7	1.6	2.0
RO	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.0	2.6	3.1	0.0	0.0	6.1	4.2	11.7	2.1
SI	0.0	0.2	0.0	0.1	2.8	4.6	0.4	0.0	7.0	7.1	5.2	2.1
SK	0.0	0.2	0.0	0.2	2.4	3.7	0.0	0.0	5.1	6.1	3.3	0.9
FI	0.2	0.4	0.0	0.1	4.5	6.0	0.0	0.0	8.3	8.5	1.2	4.0
SE	0.2	0.4	0.1	0.1	5.0	6.5	0.0	0.2	7.6	8.8	3.3	7.6
UK	0.2	0.3	0.1	0.1	2.6	3.8	0.0	0.1	6.6	7.0	3.9	4.9
IS	0.1	0.5	0.0	0.4	8.8	8.6	0.0	0.0	9.5	12.4	0.0	4.6
LI	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	9.2	z	z	0.0	0.0	z	z
NO	0.3	0.3	0.1	0.1	6.0	7.6	0.1	0.0	7.6	6.8	4.4	3.8
CH	0.1	0.2	0.0	0.1	2.4	3.5	0.0	0.0	5.8	4.8	2.5	2.7
ME	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	z	5.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	6.1	z	0.0
MK	0.0	0.4	0.0	0.0	2.1	4.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.4	33.3	16.7
AL	0.0	0.5	0.0	0.8	7.0	7.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	25.0
RS	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.0	5.0	0.0	0.0	z	4.3	z	3.1
TR	0.1	0.4	0.0	0.5	2.8	5.3	0.0	0.0	9.3	9.8	1.9	3.0
BA	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.0	7.9	7.6	0.0	0.0	11.5	5.3	z	7.7
FO	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	6.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	z	0.0	0.0	0.0
IL	0.1	0.2	0.0	0.1	3.4	4.6	0.0	0.0	9.6	8.0	2.2	2.6
MD	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.0	5.5	0.0	0.0	25.0	0.0	z	0.0

Notes: z = not applicable. All proportions are underestimated to a similar extent across countries for literature written in English. Care was taken not to bias the recall in favour of specific countries. This is because it is very difficult to extract 100% of the relevant literature using text-mining techniques without compromising accuracy. This is especially true for GDRC as the terminology used in the SSH is more generic than in other scientific areas. Source: *She Figures 2015* (European Commission, 2016), originally computed by Science-Metrix using WoS data. A comparison between the figures worldwide and those in the EU-28 reveals that the propensity to include a gender dimension in research subject matter is similar to the world average within the EU-28 Member States. The breakdown by fields of science & technology shows that the gender dimension is most common in the social sciences in 2010–2013 (6% and 7% in the EU-

28 and the world, respectively). The humanities and the medical sciences display a more modest share of publications with a gender dimension in 2010–2013 (3% to 4%), while the gender aspect is generally lacking or very minor in the agricultural sciences, engineering and technology, and natural sciences.

There is considerable country variation in the extent to which the gender dimension is addressed in national research outputs if the percentage of positive or negative departure from EU-28 or world level is considered; however, these departures (in percentage points) are generally small. The overall small differences between time periods suggest that no major advances have been made in terms of addressing the gender dimension in research. The small differences nevertheless point to increases rather than decreases.

DISCUSSION

The propensity to integrate a gender dimension into research content is generally modest, but where changes have been observed over the two time periods investigated, these point towards an increase. Unsurprisingly, a gender dimension is most likely to be taken into account is in the social sciences, and least likely in the agricultural sciences, engineering and technology, and natural sciences. For further analysis of this indicator, readers are referred to the *She Figures 2015* publication (European Commission, 2016).

A database developed by Charité Berlin indexes sex- and gender-related literature in the biomedical field. Their methodology to identify relevant literature (Oertelt-Prigione, Parol, Krohn, et al., 2010) also makes use of keyword-based query terms followed by manual validation, however only 10 highly relevant keywords were used in their study. Despite differences in the exclusion and acceptance criteria, most of the terms were consistent with those used in the present study with the exception of sexual dimorphism and sexually dimorph*. Given the focus on animal studies, the inclusion of these terms was appropriate in their case as articles using these terms in their titles or abstracts tend to be about animals, whereas the present study focuses on humans. The exclusion of such terms in the current study, even if they retrieve a few relevant papers out of their total, is not critical given the high degree of redundancy in our approach; that is, the inclusion of a wide variety of search terms that often co-occur in publications. Indeed, if a keyword is omitted, a relevant publication including this keyword will likely be captured by one of the selected search expressions.

It is important to note that this is a newly developed indicator and that any reference or target about appropriate levels of the indicator is lacking. Although it is difficult to establish a target for what could be considered ‘adequate’ content, the observed shares generally appear low. This remains true even if the GDRC dataset captures only roughly 60% of the relevant literature, implying that there is room for further increases in the future. The results presented should hence be considered as baseline levels, allowing their evolution to be monitored in the future. Additionally, relevant data at the project-level would help to further strengthen the ability to monitor changes in the inclusion of the GDRC over time, and could be linked more directly with policy initiatives in major funding programs such as Horizon 2020.

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